

**AN APPRAISAL OF THE APPLICATION OF FREEDOM OF
INFORMATION ACT (2011) AND GOVERNANCE
ACCOUNTABILITY IN NIGERIA**

¹Dr. Paul Ojo

Department of International Relations,
College of Humanities, Social and Management Sciences,
McPherson University, Seriki Sotayo, Ogun State.
ORCID ID: 0009-0009-6062-3676

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²Professor Olubunmi Ajibade

Department of Mass Communication,
College of Humanities, Social and Management Sciences,
McPherson University, Seriki Sotayo.
Corresponding Author: ojopaul97@gmail.com/ 08023035523
ORCID ID 0000-0002-8659-8263

Abstract

In a democracy, access to information by the mass media, civil society organisations and the citizens is essential for promotion of good governance. It is also a pivotal to drive sustainable development as it is a veritable tool in the government fight against corruption. The passage of Freedom of Information Act in Nigeria was regarded as a milestone in the efforts to hold government accountable for its actions and promote quality service and it is a global trend. Freedom of Information Act was signed into law by President Goodluck Jonathan on May 28, 2011 after eleven years of legislative debates. The Objective of this study was to appraise the application of the law in Nigeria in the context of its impacts on information disclosure by political office holders and public servants. Various relevant literature were reviewed. The study also adopted Transparency Theory as its theoretical framework. Findings from the study revealed that enactment of Freedom of Information Act (2011) has not made significant impact in government information disclosure. This has been attributed to the entrenched culture of secrecy in the society. As a fall out from this study, it was recommended that all stakeholders should collaborate with the Attorney General of the Federation in driving full implementation, compliance and enforcement of

the law, while sub nationals are encouraged to domesticate it. The conclusion of the study is that the law should be reformed so as to strengthen its full implementation.

Keywords: Democracy, Good governance, Global Trend, Subnational, mass media, freedom of information, and Compliance

Introduction

The place of accountability in governance cannot be over emphasized. Therefore, the foundation of good governance is to be responsive and responsible to the citizens. If there is anything that separates good governance from other forms of government, it is accountability and transparency in the conduct of the affairs of the state. The implication is that government appreciation of its obligation to the citizens and institutions that, on request, vital information is made available to them either on request or through periodical engagement of the critical stakeholders in the affairs of the state. The perception of the citizens is that business of government is shielded in secrecy away from the citizens. Also, that governance is run in a cult-like manner, where operators are not obliged to carry citizens along in the conduct of the affairs of the state.

It is against this background that after many years of pressure on government by civil society organisations, including the Nigeria Union of Journalists, Students Union and the Guild of Editors, the Nigeria Freedom of Information Act was passed in 2011 by the Nigeria National National Assembly. The passage of the bill was regarded as a significant step in the consolidation of democracy that is built around transparency, accountability and inclusiveness. Before the passage of the bill, getting information from government ministries and agencies was likened to a carmel passing through the eyes of a needle as government business was conducted in secrecy with the arrogance of the operators who felt they did not owe citizens explanations for their actions or inactions. The passage of the bill established the legal rights of the citizens to access information from any public institutions (Ajibade & Ojo, 2020)

The passage of the bill represented a significant step in the media and citizens' agitations for governance transparency and accountability. Also, the ,koki9 bill represented a break away from the past when journalists, civil society

organisations in the bid to obtain information from government ministries and departments often meet brick-wall. In a bid to obtain information and disseminate same to the public, journalists resorted to guerrilla journalism, by going underground to publish government information obtained through friendly individuals in government. Through such ingenuity in journalism practice, particularly under military administrations, media houses were burnt down while many journalists lost their lives. (Akingbulu, 2016, Isola 2010) It is therefore logical to say that lack of access to information by the citizens and media created vacuum in the constructive engagement between government and the citizens. The corollary is that governance becomes inadequate.

Before the passage of the bill which seek to seek to protect public record and interest, civil servants are scared from releasing information either to journalists or any group for fear of losing their jobs or being reprimanded. Civil servants have been investigated, suspended or even sacked for what government perceived as betrayal of trust, leaking official documents to the public as some of the information are often described as classified. According to Egielewa and Ardonojie,(2021) the bill is important, not only to media organisations but to the publics as it makes information available to them, it was meant to guarantee accessibility to information in addition to the protection of public records and personal privacy. The fear of public officers of losing their jobs if they release information to the public was allayed as the bill guarantees their protection from the consequences of their actions.

The passage of the bill was not achieved on a platter of gold as the debate was the longest legislative debate in the history of Nigeria legislative engagement as it took twelve years before the bill was eventually signed into law by President Goodluck Jonathan. It should be noted that during the administration of Olusegun Obasanjo, Civil Society Groups such as Media Rights Agenda,(MRA) Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) Nigeria Guild of Editors were at the forefront of the agitation for the enactment of the law that will give citizens and journalists access to information. These organisations were not alone, as they found support in individuals like Femi Falana, a well known Human Rights activist. Others include Edeatan Ojo and Tunde Fagbohun who was said to have taken part in the draft of the bill.(Mohammed e ta.,2023, Ugudu, 2022)

Even though the passage of the bill represented a milestone in the struggle to institute responsive and responsible government, going by the past experience when citizens and media were denied access to panel reports and their recommendations. The suppression of such documents like Uwais Report on Electoral Reform, the Okigbo Report on Gulf War windfall. In some instances, and in a bid to cover up their misdeed, government officials are said to have denied the existence of vital documents that would expose their corrupt practices. Unlike the Official Secret Act under which many journalists were jailed, and media houses shutdown, public officials were subjected to all manners of torture as public officials and journalists were punished for disseminate information, which in the eyes of the law, are legitimate rights of the citizens to know. (The News, 2005, Mohammed, etal, 2023)

Despite the passage of the law, public institutions, civil society groups and citizens have not found the process of obtaining information smooth sail as government businesses are still shrouded in secrecy, a defiant to the letters and spirit of the Freedom of Information Act.(FOI Act) According to section 29 (1) of the Act, “ All public institutions are required to make FOI reports publicly available”. Additionally, the Attorney General of the Federation has the responsibility of ensuring reports of Freedom of Information Act are accessible both physically and electronically to the citizens. Civil society Organisations have accused government agencies of blocking access to information. No doubt, this practice is a violation of the provision of the Act which establishes the right of the citizens to “ access or request information” (Ojetunde, 2020, FOI Act,2011) This study is an attempt to appraise the effectiveness of the Freedom of Information Act 2011 against the backdrop of the complaints from the media and the generality of the citizens, including human rights community.

Statement of the Problem

The philosophical basis of government accountability to the citizens has been established by Political philosophers like Hobbes and Rousseau. The theory established the substance of relationship between the citizens and the government. According to these philosophers, organization of state was as a result of agreement entered into by the society who originally had no government. Prior to this organization, community was in a state of disorder where the life of man was

solitary, poor, nasty, brutish and short. The establishment of social contract established accountability, responsibility and responsiveness. This philosophical basis strengthened the quest by the citizens to demand accountability from the government (Appadorai, 2004) The enactment of the Freedom of Information Act (2011) was driven by the need “to make public records and information, protect public records and information to the extent consistent with the public interest” Section (2) outlines documents that should be made available to citizens on request. These documents include: rules of the institution, policy statement and interpretation, recommendations and decisions, information relating to receipts and expenditure, names of salaries and their salaries, files on contracts and agreements and information relating to grants or contracts. Some of the items exempted from the Freedom the Freedom of Information Act (2011) include information on national security, law enforcement records, commercial secrets and personal privacy. (Human Rights Law Services, 2019, Oluwasemilore, 2022)

Despite the provisions in this law, citizens and civil society organisations accessibility and availability to information from ministries and agencies has remained herculean task. On request. Ministries, Department and Agencies have been accused of blocking access to vital information and documents. Even court directives are not complied with, thus government and governance in Nigeria is substantially run in secrecy, which is against democratic practices and a violation of the letters and spirit of the 1999 constitution (as amended) According to section 14(2) of the constitution, “the participation by the people in their government shall be ensured in accordance with the provisions of this constitution”. Against this background, the objectives of Freedom of Information (2011) is far from being achieved as all government institutions have found it convenient to hide vital information that could define politics of inclusion, transparency and accountability has been violated. (Oluwasemilore, 2022, Egielewa & Ardonojie, 2021, and Ajibade & Ojo, 2020)

The above observations represent the fears and misgivings expressed by the citizens about the efficacy of the Act to address the disconnect between the citizens and government which has further deepened mutual suspicion and lower trust. The passage of the bill was welcomed with optimism and high hope that it is a signal to renew hope in the relationship between the government and the

governed. (Ihejirika, 2012). But this optimism has been lost due to government tenacity from releasing information to the public. This has further reminded us of the 1962 Official Secret Act, a relic of colonial rules that represented instrument of oppression and suppression. The above misgivings about the Act form the basis of the problem for the study appraisal.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to appraise the Application of the Freedom of Information Act (2011) in the context of governance accountability in Nigeria. Other objectives are to:

- i examine the benefits of the Freedom of Information Act;
- ii investigate the extent the Freedom of Information Act has promoted accountability and transparency in governance in Nigeria; and
- iii interrogate the challenges confronting the implementation of the Freedom of Information Act

Research Questions

The study will seek to answer the following questions:

- i what are the benefits of the Freedom of Information Act?
- ii to what extent has the Freedom of Information Act promoted accountability and transparency in governance in Nigeria?
- iii what are the challenges confronting the implementation of the Freedom of Information Act?

Literature Review

According to section 49 of the 1999 constitution (as amended), “every person shall be entitled to freedom of expression, including freedom to hold and to receive and impart ideas and information without interference”. This position is further consolidated by section 14 (2) of the 1999 constitution (as amended) which provides that “the participation by the people in their government shall be ensured in accordance with the provisions of the constitution”. With the advent of constitutional democracy, the foundation for citizens’ engagement was laid. The

laying of the foundation for free press and citizens' engagement was predicated on the symbiotic roles of the citizens and mass media in agenda setting and in the education of the citizens.

Media practitioners and citizens that are critical of government policies and programmes in Nigeria have not been spared from the guillotine. While some newspapers have been proscribed and journalists arrested for their publications and editorial opinions, in most cases under military, media and citizens that are critical of government policies have been subjected to physical and psychological torture. Old laws like the Official Secret Act of 1962 became the weapon for the harassment and proscription of newspaper and magazines. The Act provides "that any person who transmits any classified matter to a person to whom he is not authorized on behalf of the government to transmit it" or obtains, reproduces, or retains any classified matter, which he is not authorized on behalf of the government to obtain, reproduce or retain as the case may be, shall be guilty of an offence" No doubt the advance of the law was a reminder of the colonial legacies as contained in the Secret Ordinances of 1897.(Newswatch,1987, Abdulkadir etal.2025) this law became a ready tool in the hands of military government as media houses such as Punch, National Concord, News watch and the News Magazines became the victims of the obnoxious act.

The use of this law was not enough to silence journalism practice as many of them went underground to practice what they called guerrilla journalism. While some journalists lost their lives, for some, it was their families that became target of attack and torture. Coming from this horrible past, the passage of the Freedom of Information Act was seen as a new era in the citizen/ government relationship. And regarded as the appreciation of citizens, media and civil society organisations participation in their own governmental affairs. (Popoola, 2003) According to Ekpou (2001) passage of Freedom of Information Act is a freedom for all citizens as democracy is distinguished from other forms of government by the citizens engagement with government in a transparent manner. Therefore, freedom of Information Act is freedom for the rule of law.

The passage of Freedom of Information Bill was meant to change public office culture on record keeping. It is a known fact that record keeping culture is very poor in Nigeria despite technological development, which has aided record

keeping. Section 2(2) and 9 (2) of the Act seeks to promote preservation of information by public officers. This is a novel departure from the past where public officers are least care about the safety of public documents and properties. This lack of personal attachment to public institution and their operations has done incalculable damage in terms of documentation manipulation and outright destruction of files to cover unethical conduct.

According to Abdulkadir etal (2025) free access to information and the dissemination of same to the public by mass media is a fundamental pillar of promoting the truth, which the objective of informing and educating the public. Furthermore, the Libertarian, a philosophical school of thought on free press submitted that it is a democratic way of empowering the media to publish news items unhindered. The press is at liberty to publish anything, anywhere and anyhow. The advocate of unrestraint press is a call to anarchy and irresponsible journalism. While access and availability of information is necessary for the promotion of political inclusion, growth and development, conduct of civil society and the media in the management is very important taking into consideration legal implications of news release and form of publication as aggrieved individual and even government officials could sue for libel as all actions should be guided and conducted with all sense of civility.

In his postulation, Daramola (2003) submitted that the strength of the media is in its ability to reveal happenings in government to the public without censorship or blockades. He further stressed that free press add values to government and the society at large as individuals are free to express their views on government programmes and policies. Therefore, a virile press makes governance dynamic and people oriented. If mass media practitioners are to approximate the degree of responsibilities placed on them, then the regulatory institutions like Nigeria Union of Journalists, Guild of Editors, should insist strict compliance with the ethics of the profession, which is built on authenticity, credibility and representativeness. Inability of mass media to conduct itself within the ethics of its profession has driven the profession to the mud. Public institutions are afraid of releasing information to media houses because of the fear that such information could be sensationalized to achieve political or commercial interests of the media house.

Mass media access to information is determined by many factors, such as structure of ownership and editorial policy. For instance, government owned mass media, such as Nigeria Television Authority (NTA) are favoured to enjoy patronage from government officials and politicians in programmes coverage and newsreporting. Since the person that pays piper dictates the tune. The tendency to moderate their reportage on government sensitive official matters could be predicted as the consequences of a breach could be predicted, including termination of career.

Prior to the enactment of the law, existing laws such as Official Secret Act, Evidence Act and Criminal Code amongst others seemed to have “caged” public officers from releasing official documents to the public. Even though these laws are antithetical to democracy, the objective was to ensure vital government documents are not leaked to the public. Relying on the laws stated above, National Assembly investigations have suffered set back due to deliberate refusal of officials to avail the representatives of the people necessary documents. These actions are carried without consequences. Though under the new bill, there are varying degree of sanctions including administrative and court actions, yet no sanction has been imposed on officials of Ministries, Department and Agencies that have not honoured request for documents. While government agencies in Nigeria have blocked access to information, either for journalists, private citizens and civil society organisations. (Ojetunde, 2020, Asunka & Logan,2021)

Importance of public access to information was reinforced with the recognition and endorsement by the African Commission on Human and Peoples’ Rights and the Pan African Parliament. These bodies position was informed by the conviction of the impact of access to information will have on service delivery, which is an issue of strong debate in many Africa public service. Attempt to promote good service delivery has motivated journalists in many Africa countries from exposing the activities and conduct of their public servants, as it was reported during elections in Nigeria. In some cases, this has not gone down well with political leaders as such actions are perceived as journalists working with opposition parties to bring down government or water down the legitimacy of the electoral process (Emmanuel, 2025, Asunka & Logan, 2021)

The intrigues and maneuvers that characterized Freedom of Information (FOI) pointed to the fact that politicians are not disposed to the implementation of the law as such law could be an impediment and diversionary to the “good works” their doing. However, Freedom of Information Act has been in use in the USA. The usage of the law has been a source of worry to the congress as the implementation of law has gone beyond what it was intended to serve, particularly in the areas of the cost of administration in terms of the number of cases the state have had to face. Another western country that has adopted freedom of information is Canada. The Access to Information Act came into effect in 1982, with exemptions in some areas like security matters. The adoption of the law by many countries is a way to open up political space for more public engagements. Approaches to the implementation of this law has shown that there is need to represent socio-cultural orientation of the people. (Popoola, 2012, Ajibade & Ojo, 2020)

Hadiza (2018) posited that FOI represents tool for promoting national development. Furthermore, she acknowledged the roles of Civil Society Organisations who were at the forefront of the campaign to realize the passage of the law. He equally alluded to the fact that these CSOs have continued to play pivotal roles in the sensitization of the public on the importance of the law.

The coordinator of Right to Know, Enoche submitted that freedom of information will enhance speedy dispensation of justice as the law will enable investigators unrestricted access to information and with such access, investigation will be faster, thereby promoting quick dispensation of justice.

Theoretical Framework

To assist this study in its proper explanations, the Transparency Theory will be adopted as theoretical framework. The theory was developed by political scientist, but it has gained popularity in the corporate world and has been adopted into governance. What the theory seeks to promote is openness and responsiveness of leadership in the discharge of their assignments. The argument of the theory is that organization and stakeholders need complete and verifiable information for planning and sustainability, as such will reduce unethical conduct.

Applying this theory in the context of the Freedom of Information Act, (2011), the objective of the stakeholders, particularly mass media and civil society organisations is to promote transparency, advance the tenets of democracy that is built around accountability and inclusiveness. While the theory seeks to achieve total transparency, the nature of our society may not allow full attainment of the objective which the theory aimed to attain. (Scott & Albert, 2016)

Appraisal of the Application of Freedom of Information Act in Nigeria

The quest for freedom of information in Nigeria has taken a tortuous journey. The interest generated by the citizens, civil society organisations could be understood against the backdrop of the harrowing experience of mass media and human right activists in the era of military rule. The hoarding of information from the press and lack of constructive engagement between citizens and government even with the advent of democracy was a thing of concern to all citizens clamouring for good and inclusive governance. The interest generated from the citizens and other stakeholders could be understood against this backdrop. The fact it was passed by legislators at federal level, does not exempt the sub national government from domesticating it. While some states like Ekiti state have domesticated it many states are yet to adopt it into their statute book. (Habib, 2025)

Freedom of Information Act has gone down as one of the longest legislative debates in the history of Nigeria. The bill was eventually signed into law on May 28, 2011 by President Goodluck Jonathan. The demand for unrestricted access to information was in line with the provision of the UNESCO which seeks to promote freedom of expression and government provision of quality information to the citizens. Underlining the position of UNESCO is the demand for accountability, openness and good governance. The objectives of Freedom of Information Act is in tandem with the objectives of UNESCO, which include:

- a. Enable people to have informed opinion and to engage in full and open debates;
- b. Ensured government activities are scrutinized;
- c. Participation of journalists and civil society groups; and
- d. Promoting improved and quality service in the public service.

No doubt, the signing of the law by president Goodluck Jonathan was a demonstration of strong political will and practical show of willingness to expand political space for citizens constructive engagement. Section 1 of the law provides for the “right of any person to access or request information whether or not contained in any written form, which is in the custody or possession of any public officials, agency or institution however described, is established”. With the establishment of the right of citizens to demand access to government record and information, the legal basis was laid. This request was further strengthened by the provision in the law that protect public servants from any legal or administrative consequences arising from disclosing or releasing information to media organisations, civil society organisations or the citizens.(Udoudo, etal. 2020)

While the intention was to strengthening good and accountable governance, thereby increasing the level of trust between citizens and government, the implementation of the law has suffered set back due to non-adherence to its provisions. Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) have been accused by civil society groups and media houses of blocking request for information. On several occasions, request from federal or state legislators from MDAs to facilitate the performance of their oversight are hardly honoured. Against the provisions of the Freedom of Information Act, salaries and allowances of public office holders are kept from the public and media. In their submission, Ajibade and Ojo (2020) attributed the hoarding of information to the society entrenched culture of secrecy. The unwillingness of government agencies to release information was further worsened by the political office holders at all level tha are aversed to the release of vital information to the public because of the dust such documents may raise due to their corrupt practices. In some cases, Ministries, Departments and Agencies have been accused of defying court rulings, even when they receive official request for information. (Uthman,2024)

Section 29(1) enjoined public institutions to submit annual reports of their activities to the Attorney General of the Federation, (AGF) who will in turn make them available to the public. Ministries, Departments and Agencies are expected to submit these reports in February of every year. These reports are submitted late and AGF hardly make the reports available to the public. The non compliance with the provisions of the law will affect the effective implementation of the law.

No doubt, if this section of the law is adhered to, it will electoral integrity and government fight against corruption.

On the legal front, freedom of information act has witnessed judicial set back with the rulings of Justice Gabriel Kolawole of the Abuja Federal High court, in the case between Paradigm Initiative Nigeria and Dr. Reuben Abati, where his lordship averred that the Section 1(2) of the Freedom of Information Act should be amended as such amendment will require those seeking information from public institution will be required to demonstrate their interest. Such provision may be counter-productive and run contrary to the objective of the freedom of information act that seeks to guarantee the right of the citizens to have access to public information. (Edeatan,2013)

Freedom of Information has suffered a set backs in Nigeria due to lack of political will of political office holders to sustain the provisions of the law and the fears that it was a media law targeted at the political class. Much as this position is condemnable, it is also an appreciation of the pre-independence and post-independence historical roles of the media in Nigeria and Africa at large. Nigeria press and human right activists were torn in the flesh of military and their watchdog roles is seen as an overreach instead of building partnership with the press. Nevertheless, Nigeria press and civil society organisations cannot be exonerated from the politics as some of them have been classified as the agent of the establishment. (Isola, 2010, Abdulkadir,2025,Tell,1997). In spite of the limitations placed by political class, on the implementation of the law due to lack of awareness and bureaucratic bottlenecks, the law has increased the consciousness on the political class and public servants on the need to be discreet in the way they conduct themselves. Though political class and bureaucrats are reluctant in releasing information to the press and relevant stakeholders, yet it has empowered journalists to demand for accountability. In the final analysis, the implementation and success of Freedom of Information Bill in Nigeria is a mixed bag. The skepticism that trailed the passage of the law may not be unconnected with past experience where activities of mass media has led to shedding of blood as it was the case in the unauthorized and false declation of election results by Jeremi FM in Warri (Abudkadir,etal.2025,Ajibade & Ojo,2020, Akingbulu,2016) While appreciating the FOI act as law that was meant to change the face of

governance, the non-compliance has necessitated calls for the reform of the FOI in order to enhance compliance and enforcement.

Discussion of the Findings

The main objective of this study is to appraise how Freedom of Information Act is being applied in the conduct of government businesses as the perception of the generality of the citizens is that in Nigeria, government businesses at all levels are shrouded in secrecy with little or no commitment of the officials to render account of their services to the public. The non compliance of the ruling class to drive governance on the tenets of democracy that are built on transparency and accountability has exacerbated corruption and promote inefficiency and poor quality service. Agitations for Freedom of Information law in Nigeria begun with the collaborative efforts of civil society organisations like the Media Right Agenda (MRA), Civil Liberties Organisation (CLO) and the Nigeria Union of Journalists (NUJ) The campaigns of these organisations were driven with the objective that FOI will serve as tool for Nigerians to demand for accountability and transparency in governance. It was also driven by good for the citizens to demand for quality service from public servants as Ministries, Departments and Agencies are buoyed down bureaucratic bottleneck. The study has assisted the research in appreciating the benefits of FOI in the promotion of accountability and transparency in government. (Abioye, 2019, The Nation,2021)

Findings from the study revealed that even-though there have been substantial non compliance from organisations, yet through the activities of civil society organisations and other agencies of the state, watchdog roles have been imposed on all segment of the society. Government organisations have become more careful in the manner issues are handled. The law provides that “any person entitled to information under this Act, shall have the right to institute proceedings in the court to compel any public institution to comply with the provision of this Act”.This provision seeks promote accountability.(Ajibade & Ojo,2020, Habib,2025) Notwithstanding the initial hiccups, technology has also imposed some level of restraints on government officials as they could be caught in the act through the deployment of modern technology.

In line with the research question, findings from the study indicates that Freedom of Information Act (2011) faced the challenges of implementation, compliance and enforcement. Government agencies have been accused of blocking requests from organisations and individual citizens. This is a contravention of the provision of the law, particularly section 1 (2). In view of the importance of the law, subnational governments ought to have domesticated it, but only two states, Lagos and Ekiti have domesticated it. The challenge of compliance could also be attributed to lack of awareness on the part of public office holders or deliberate attempt to continue in the old ways of perpetuating corruption and display of naked arrogance to ignore transparency and accountability, which are two strong pillars on which democracy and good governance are laid.(Habib,2025, FOI Act,2011, Egielewa etal,2021,Ojetunde,2020)

Freedom of Information is a global practice. Countries adopt it to drive good governance and accountability. Not minding the roles of stakeholders, such as media, civil society organisations and citizens, and their good intention, public institutions block information because some of these stakeholders do not draw the lines between national interest and sensational reportings. Which could run contrary to national security. (Udoudo etal,2020, Abioye, 2019)

Conclusion

Access to information is the right of every Nigerian. This right is enshrined in the 1999 constitution (as amended) it is also guaranteed by the Africa Union Charter on Human and Peoples Right. It is on the basis of this legal framework that various organisations such as the Media Rights Agenda, (MRA) the Civil Liberty Organisation (CLO) pushed for the enactment of Freedom of Information. It is also in accordance with global practice, particularly western democracy and many African countries. This law was eventually passed into law after eleven years. The passage of this law represented a significant shift in Nigerians' drive for transparency and accountability in governance. In spite of the legal backing, the law has suffered from implementation, compliance and enforcement. With the passage of law, information on asset declaration was supposed to be made available to the public, while the Attorney General of the Federation (AGF) is bound by the provision of the law to make annual reports of government Ministries, Department and Agencies available to the public. This provision has

not been adhered to while attempt by the public to obtain information on government activities are often blocked. The reluctance to release information to the public by government establishment has been attributed to Nigeria entrenched culture of secrecy. No doubt, this is an attempt to sustain corruption and poor service delivery. (Ajibade &Ojo,2020, FOI Act,2011)

In view of the public outcry against the implementation of the law, coupled with the fact that only two states, Lagos and Ekiti have domesticated the law, is another set back on the successful implementation of the law. Hence the conclusion of this study is that the objective of the freedom of Information, which is to promote good governance through citizens' access to unhindered information about government is far from being realized. It is against this failure to achieve its objectives that Nigerians have called for the reform of the law with a view to strengthening its application, enforcement and compliance. (Abioye, 2019, Habib, 2025)

Recommendations

Globally, government appreciates its responsibility in continuous engagement and improvement in quality service and good government. This study has examined Freedom of Information Act 2011 in the context of the historical roles it was intended to play in Nigeria democracy. Eventhough it has not meant the threshold that was intended by the stakeholders, yet the introduction of the law could be described as a right step in the right direction. Arising from this study, the following recommendations are made:

- a. Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) should establish Quality Assurance Department with the mandate to ensure that provisions of FOI Act (2011) are implemented, complied with and enforced. This will promote transparency and build citizens' confidence in the government;
- b. To ensure the domestication of the Act at subnational level, National and State Assemblies, office of the Attorney General of the Federation, Civil Society Organisations in conjunction State Ministries of Justice should collaborate in educating bureaucrats and political office holders on the importance of the law and what they stand to gain through the implementation of the law.

- c. One of the fears of the political class is the tendency of media and civil Society Organisations to abuse the right to know. There is the need for proper scrutiny of materials obtained, as they affect national security and the integrity of Nigeria public institutions. To this end, there is the need for media and civil society organisations to work together.

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